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An Appraisal of Housing Policies Performances in Nigeria: Associated Problems and Past Efforts of Government

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Abstract:

Housing, like food and clothing, is a basic human requirement. A person's well-being, survival, and health depend on it. This study appraised housing policies performances in Nigeria, with examination of associated problems and past efforts of government. Content analysis and assessment techniques were utilized to gather and analyze credible and valid data on Nigerian housing policy concerns and housing condition outcomes in this expository research. Nigeria's housing policies and problems were analyzed using books, existing records, published works in the form of yearly reports and reviews and government documents, as well as academic articles on housing studies in general and conference papers from the field. Research found that Nigeria's policies and programs have made significant gains in the creation and supply of housing. There are a number of faults in the policies and programs despite the fact that poverty, growing construction and building material costs and homelessness, poor policy structures for housing provision, administrative backlogs in building permit and receipt of certificate of occupancy are among them. The study recommended that Nigeria's housing policy must be examined on a regular basis in order to ensure that it is functional and acceptable to the public. Other than that, in order to achieve effective housing provision, there must be accessibility to land, financing, and construction supplies. Infrastructure, housing maintenance, and incentives for

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insurance companies should also be provided to support affordable home development. Low-income households should be considered in the development of housing policy among others.

Keywords: Housing, Housing Policies, Housing Policies Performances, Nigeria,

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Introduction

In the last three decades, the population of Nigeria, particularly in the cities, has grown phenomenally without a corresponding growth in housing units, resulting in a severe shortage of livable homes. There is a horrible atmosphere as a result of overcrowding as well as bad living circumstances, increased poverty rates and social vices, etc. In many developing nations, public housing projects fail to offer enough, affordable, and high-quality housing for the target population (Ruonavaara, 2018; Hansson, 2018). Governments in developing nations, on the other hand, are reported to be pressing ahead with efforts to solve the issue of providing suitable, affordable, and long-term housing (Eerola & Saarimaa, 2018; Clapham, 2018). According to El-Hadj, et al (2018), ensuring that everyone has access to decent housing is a shared responsibility that involves not only governments, but also the private sector, non-governmental organizations, municipalities and other regional or local authorities, as well as international organizations and NGOs.

Housing, like food and clothing, is a basic human requirement (Barker, 2019). A person's well-being, survival, and health depend on it (Mukhtar et al., 2000). A person's status in society might be determined by the quality of his or her residence. The standing of a man in society can be influenced by where he lives and the sort of house he has, shelter is essential to human existence (Wapwera et al., 2017). According to Wapwera et al. (2017), housing is defined as having the ability to have access to land, shelter, and the amenities essential to make the shelter practical, convenient, visually pleasing, safe and hygienic. A lack of proper housing can negatively impact a person's health, safety, and personal privacy. Invariably, the housing sector's performance is used as a gauge of a nation's health (Ezennia & Hoskara, 2019; Mukhtar, et al., 2016).

In both rural and urban parts of Nigeria, there is a wide range of housing issues. Rural areas have a housing shortage because of the quality of the housing stock, whereas metropolitan areas face a shortage of quantity. Qualitative shortcomings such as location, degree of goodness, and house value all play a role in rural housing challenges. As stated by Kampamba et al. (2018), rural housing is incomplete since social services are not sufficiently linked to them such as power, water, and transportation.

High urbanization, an ever-increasing number of urban dwellers, and the rising demands of Nigerians all contribute to the country's housing shortage. More specifically, Lawal and Adekunle (2018) found that the most pressing urbanization challenges are inadequate housing, unplanned construction and inefficient upkeep of existing structures, ageing, and the lack of social infrastructure. Homes in urban core regions are also characterized by a lack of suitable infrastructural facilities, such as poor ventilation, no in-built toilets or kitchens, and a poor trash disposal system. Lack of planning, the emergence of shanty settlements, and the availability of decaying dwellings are further issues related with urban housing.

There are many issues with housing in Nigeria, including poverty, discrimination against using indigenous materials, ineffectual housing financing, inadequate financial instruments for mobilizing funds, high building material costs and a lack of infrastructure facilities, as well as bureaucracies in acquiring land, processing of certificates of occupancy (C of O), and approval of construction plans. Some of the other obstacles to housing creation, upkeep, and delivery include a lack of good planning; ineffective government programs and regulations; uncontrolled private sector engagement; weak policy structures and poor research and

technology into housing (Smets & van Lindert, 2016). It has been suggested that housing is linked to a wide range of problematic social and economic phenomena, including inflation, income policy, and the other difficulties (Smets & van Lindert, 2016). However, the ever-increasing demand cannot be matched by supply as a result of all of these issues.

Literature Review

As argued by Daniel and Hunt (2014), the primary goal of urban and rural land use planning is to provide a more practical, aesthetically beautiful, and economically feasible physical environment for people to live, work, play, and move around in. The housing strategy recognized that a key issue in Nigeria is the lack of suitable housing in accordance with the town planning regulations (Aliu, et al., 2018) as both qualitative and quantitative deficits exist in urban and rural areas, hence, poor environmental quality and deterioration in human health will result (Ebekoziem, 2020).

According to Eerola (2021), laws, regulations, and administrative procedures that facilitate the construction and distribution of homes constitute a housing policy. This policy was also formulated in accordance with the basic ideals of freedom, fairness, equity and authority as well as public interest. Nigeria's housing crisis is the primary focus of the policy. Like other policies, has a set of objectives and a plan for achieving them. All Nigerians should have access to safe, decent, and affordable housing as a main objective of the national housing policy. Land ownership, financing, construction, and delivery were all covered under the policy (Eerola, 2021).

For a successful housing policy to be implemented, the role of government must be considered, and this can include everything from land use planning and control to financial and credit assistance, subsidies to low-income groups, rent control and more. The government can also be involved at specific stages or when solutions are needed for specific problems, such as land use plans and controls to financial assistance and credit aids, subventions to low-income groups, and rent control (Iheme, et al., 2015)

Oyebanji, et al (2017) indicated that the strategy placed a high priority on ensuring that people had access to essential amenities such as drinkable water and transportation, as well as electricity. Decree No. 53, which came into effect in December of 1989, also established a legal foundation for the functioning of Nigeria's principal mortgage institutions. As a result, the policy permits the government, non-governmental groups, and community-based organizations to work together on housing projects. Additionally, tax breaks on home equity loans and other financial aid were made available to home builders. Housing policies encouraged using local building materials, as well. Overall, Nigeria's housing strategy has been able to address some of the country's housing issues (Oyebanji, et al., 2017).

According to Festus and Amos (2015), the government's efforts in formulating and implementing the National Housing Policy have been noteworthy so far. Many Nigerians are still living in dilapidated and squalid conditions despite the government's best attempts to improve the situation. According to recent studies (Iheme, 2017; Ebekoziem, 2021) on the subject, it is impossible to solve the housing shortage. Homeless individuals can be found in even the wealthiest countries. Forced eviction and homelessness are typical occurrences in Nigeria's major cities, such as Lagos, Kano, Port Harcourt, Ibadan, Owerri, and Kaduna, as well as several smaller towns. A population of more than 180 million and a city population of more than 35 percent make the housing situation extremely difficult. In fact, Saidu and Yeom

(2020) predicted that by 2025, more than 62% of Nigerians will be residing in urban areas, given a population growth rate of 2.8%. A lack of housing, squalor, overpopulation, and bad living conditions characterize metropolitan areas today.

Abandoned housing developments, non-implementation of housing policies, and a disregard for the poor characterize housing at the national level. Oluleye, et al. (2020) cited a lack of resources as a major problem, along with affordability. Other issues with housing provision in Nigeria are linked to policy instrument flaws and the consequences of such flaws. The challenges in house delivery can also be traced back to administrative constraints. The country has implemented a number of housing regulations and programs in order to address these issues. In terms of ensuring that everyone has adequate access to quality housing, Nigeria's housing policy reform currently faces a key dilemma: how to establish a delicate equilibrium between market reforms, government interference, and social mechanisms. As part of economic restructuring and reforms, the government is enacting deregulation measures in the financial markets (forex, commodities, commerce, and investment), as well as in the manufacturing sector (housing construction).

Research Methodology

A content analysis and assessment approach was utilized to gather and analyze trustworthy data on Nigerian housing policy concerns and housing condition outcomes in this expository research project. Researchers focused on gathering, analyzing, and appraising materials linked to the National Housing Policy of Nigeria (1991) and associated revision and implementation strategy documents. Nigeria's housing policies and problems were analyzed using books, existing records, written articles in the form of yearly reports and reviews and government documents, as well as academic articles on housing studies in general and conference papers from the field.

Results and Discussion

Housing Policies Performances in Nigeria

In 2003, the government of Nigeria redoubled its efforts to address the country's longstanding housing and urban development challenges by expanding the roles of several major housing delivery agencies and establishing a new Federal Ministry of Housing and Urban Development (from Ministry of Works and Housing). Table 1 below summarizes the accomplishments of Nigeria's housing policy over the country's five decades of independence to offer a different viewpoint on the country's housing history and performance.

Table 1: Housing Policies Performances in Nigeria

HOUSING PROGRAMME	MAIN FEATURES / PROJECTIONS	MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS/ OUTPUT
National Development Plan (NDP-1) 1962-68	Industrial Estates, land acquisition, and Town Planning produced 24,000 housing units during the period.	As of 1967, only 500 units had been constructed. A performance level of 2.1%.
NDP-2 (1970-74)	As a result, housing became a source of social and political tension. The federal and state military governments should create and rent	A federal housing authority has been set up (FHA). Until 1976, the FHA was unable to function. More than 55,000

	<p>affordable housing for their personnel. Lagos will get 10,000 units, while the capitals of the other 11 states would get 4,000 units apiece. Distribution of housing units in accordance with socioeconomic groups: Low-income families make up 60%; middle-income families are 25%; and the high-income group is 15%. Additional government housing has been promised but has yet to be built. Loans for private homes for federal personnel have been revived and expanded. Additional government investment in the manufacturing of cement and other building supplies, as well as more importation of cement to meet the increased demand for cement from new house construction.</p>	<p>homes have been built in around 80 estates across the country, and the FHA has a land holding of about 11,000 hectares. The Federal Housing Administration has invested about N=32 billion in housing projects and supporting infrastructure.</p>
<p>NDP-3 (1975-80)</p>	<p>202, 000 dwelling units would be created each year, with 46,000 units in Lagos, 12,000 in Kaduna, and 8,000 in the other 17 state capitals; this is a total of 202, 000 homes every year. The FHA was responsible for providing the necessary infrastructure for the states to build the mandated number of units. It was a first for the Federal Housing Administration. For housing only, a new ministry was established: the Ministry of Housing, National Development and Environment (HNDE). Additional funding for the Federal Housing Administration (FHA) was provided for the efficient takeoff of direct building and growth of housing estates in several areas of the United States. For the first time in its history, Lagos State's civilian administration launched a five-year state housing</p>	<p>The actual number of units completed was 37,650. Representing a successful performance percentage of around 19%. Lagos State completed 47,200 units. In Nigeria's history of housing delivery, 94% is an exceptional mark.</p>

	plan for 50, 000 units in 1979. (1979-1983).	
NDP- 4 (1981-85)	To produce 2,000 housing units yearly in each of the 19 states of the federation	
National Housing Policy 1991	By the year 2000, all Nigerians should be able to afford or have access to suitable housing. To eliminate the housing problem by the year 2000, 730, 000 new dwelling units must be built each year. All levels of government were encouraged and encouraged to participate in the delivery of housing. Institutions within the scheme were strengthened to operate in a more efficient manner. a focus on investments in housing that meet the most basic requirements boosted private sector involvement in the construction of new homes With a start-up grant of N250 million, the National Housing Fund was officially established in 1992.	NO VISIBLE IMPACT
National Housing Program (1994-95)	Construction of 121,000 housing units for all income levels is planned. Newly formed state governments were given 5,000 units each, while the remaining 21 states were given 76,000 units.	Only 1,014 units were completed.
National Housing Policy (2002)	Expanded access to long-term, sustainable housing financing for all Nigerians by developing the mortgage finance industry. Initiated and promoted the involvement of Nigeria's Real Estate Developers Association (REDAN) in the provision of affordable housing in the country. to make it easier for state housing agencies to take a more active role in the provision of low-cost homes Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs)	There has been no discernible impact to date. More than 14 million housing units remain unsold in the United States. According to HABITAT (2005), Nigerian home mortgages account for less than 1% of the country's total gross domestic product (GDP).

	have improved the housing supply chain. A restructured FMBN has been established to allow the secondary market operation of capital market platforms to provide long-term mortgage funding. The newly formed Ministry of Housing and Urban Development has been given responsibility for housing.	
State Housing Corporations, States Owned Mortgage Banks, and States Housing Ministries	Almost all of Nigeria's state governments now have their own housing corporation, which they run well. Mortgage banks are also owned by most states, in addition to their housing corporations. In some cases, these two institutions have been forced to work together with state ministries of land, housing, and urban development, FHA, FMBN, the African Development Bank (ADB), housing development-based NGOs, and organized private developers through Public Private Partnership (PPP) arrangements. It is most common to use the BOT approach (Build, Operate, and Transfer).	All of Nigeria's states, as well as the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), have received a total of 3,705 housing units from the joint efforts of these institutions. ASK FOR DETAILS ON LSDPC, ANHCOL, the International Monetary Fund (IMF), KOGGI, etc.
FMBN	N100 billion in first-ever housing bonds, issued in two installments of N5 million apiece, have been issued. To comply with monetization policy, the money was utilized to let federal government employees buy non-essential homes in Abuja and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT).	The acquisition of almost 30,000 housing units was financed by the federal government.

Sources: Eerola (2021)

Problems Associated with Housing Policies in Nigeria

Execution and insufficient research on the policy's formulation and implementation, insufficient funding, a lack of skilled personnel in the building industry and a lack of infrastructure amenities are some of the difficulties related with the national housing policy, according to Lawal and Adekunle (2018) and Iheme (2017). Many other issues, such as rural-to-urban migration and a high rapid urbanisation, lack of effective planning, the growth of shanty towns, and the availability of substandard buildings, are discussed in Ebekozien (2021) and Saidu and Yeom (2020), respectively. Despite government efforts, housing

shortages can be seen in both urban and rural areas. Rural-to-urban migration is a major factor in urban housing shortages. Adding to the difficulty is a naturally occurring population increase and the lack of impact of the housing strategy in rural areas. Houses in rural areas are typically in disrepair, with basic amenities such as running water, toilets, and a somewhat clean environment being the most common complaints (Festus & Amos, 2015).

For the same reasons, Oyebanji, et al. (2017) argued that land is the most important component of any housing plan. It has a significant impact on both the supply and demand of housing. All Nigerian towns have a high cost of land, and this problem is exacerbated by delays in the processing of Certificates of Occupancy (C of O) and clearance of construction plans. Other difficulties, such as low wages, high mortgage interest rates, high building material costs, a preference for imported building materials, and a lack of social services exacerbate this issue. In addition to environmental protection, social integration, and urban security and governance, the housing policy falls short in these areas. Above all, the country's ever-changing socioeconomic and political realities present a challenge to the policy (Oluleye, et al., 2020).

It has also been noted by Oluleye (2020) that the national housing strategy is not able to solve both the quantity and quality of housing issues. The ever-increasing demand for housing, which is not being fulfilled by the available supply, is a major contributor to the quality and quantity shortages (Oyebanji, et al., 2017). The housing market's inertia is to blame for its inability to fulfill rising demand. As a result of this, there is a housing shortage in both urban and rural areas; hence, a strong housing policy becomes even more critical. So, an approach that addresses poverty, efficient and effective housing finance, availability of land, high costs of building materials and environmental management, as well as access to basic social services and other institutional mechanisms for housing delivery is needed.

Why Past Market-Efforts of Government Failed and May Still Fail

Poverty

It was pointed out by Aliu, et al. (2018) that planners of the housing programs did not take into considerations that the buildings they were about to create were intended for the poor. If they had, they would have seen that the houses they built were out of reach for those with less financial resources. They should have taken into account their financial situation.

High Cost of Housing Units

At a time when the middle and low-income groups were making less than N5000 a day, the housing units were put on the market at excessive prices. Middle and low-income individuals would have needed at least a lifetime to accumulate such a sum. Because of this, they tended to focus on slums (Eerola, 2021).

Access to Credit Facilities

According to Iheme, et al. (2015), both the government and private mortgage lenders refused to provide credit to people with low incomes. Low-income people lacked the collateral necessary by these organizations and hence were unable to meet the onerous administrative requirements.

Low Incentive to Investors

Lawal and Adekunle (2018) pointed out that poor incentives to investors are another reason why previous housing interventions have failed. They are rational and profit-oriented persons. The pleading of others is not enough for them. Even if the economic climate is

favorable, there is no need to invest if there is no return on the investment. Investors prefer to keep their money in the bank if they cannot make a profit, so the government should provide tax breaks and other incentives. There is insufficient effective demand in Nigeria's housing sub-sector. Lawal and Adekunle (2018) predicted that a two-bedroom flat would sell for N2.8 million. Sadly, most people who can afford such a large sum of money prefer to build their own house rather than go through the arduous process of purchasing a ready-to-go residence. Cities like Port Harcourt, Aba, Lagos, and Onitsha are no strangers to this. As a result, an average worker thinks that with the same amount of money he/she will be able to progressively build up a three-bedroom flat or more in the near future. This means that individuals who can afford a two-bedroom home are not a part of the market demand for housing in Nigeria, while those who ask for it are unable to properly demand for it and make up the market demand. Because of this, entrepreneurs in the sub-sector have little or no motivation to participate. In fact, the country's large number of vacant homes serves as a sufficient deterrent to potential investors.

Housing Units Sited at the Periphery

National Low-Cost Housing (NLCH) programs are located on the periphery of cities, resulting in an increased cost of commuting to and from work for occupants who are city workers (Ebekozi, 2020). People who lived in these areas had to endure a lot of hardship and unhappiness as a result of lack of basic necessities like water, power, and well-maintained roads. This is why the worker would rather squat with family and friends in the city or reside in the slums.

Rural-Urban Drift

Rural-to-urban migration in Nigeria is another element that contributes to the country's housing woes. As more and more people move to cities in search of a better life, the cities become even more congested and their infrastructure becomes increasingly overburdened. Housing shortages in the country have already reached 34 million units (Eerola, 2021). Because of the current rural infrastructure conditions, it is unlikely that the housing programs will be able to succeed in the near future.

Conclusion

In conclusion, regardless of one's financial situation, a place to call home is an absolute necessity. Despite this, there is an inherent housing shortage which can be found in both urban and rural areas in Nigeria. Slum habitation, homelessness, overcrowding, squatter settlements, and poor housing units are all forms of urban housing problems in Nigeria. Rural areas are plagued by low-quality housing, bad environmental conditions, and a lack of infrastructure. One option to address the housing crisis is through the use of policy instruments. Nigerian Housing Policy was enacted in 1991 to solve the country's housing shortages in this way. In the Nigerian housing strategy, practicality, affordability, and a limited time schedule for the implementation of the programs were all taken into consideration. Nigeria's housing policies and programs have been capable of making considerable improvements in the production and delivery of housing to some extent. Nevertheless, the policies and programs are besieged by flaws such as poverty, rising construction and building material costs, homelessness, weak policy structures for housing provision, administrative backlogs in building permit and receipt of certificate of occupancy, programme review and monitoring and lots more.

Recommendations

The primary goal of housing program is to alleviate the burdens of homelessness. In order to accomplish this, the policy must be improved in order to be effective. As a result, Nigeria's housing policy must be examined on a regular basis in order to ensure that it is functional and acceptable to the public. Other than that, in order to achieve effective housing provision, there must be accessibility to land, financing, and construction supplies. Infrastructure, housing maintenance, and incentives for insurance companies should also be provided to support affordable home development. Low-income households should be considered in the development of housing policy. As a result, low-cost housing for low-income families should be made available.

Encouragement of locally sourced construction materials should be prioritized when designing for low-income households. Furthermore, a realistic housing goal must take into account slum upgrading, regular maintenance, and urban regeneration. Institutional structures, housing finance, low-income rural housing, and urban model government housing should all be included in housing delivery methods. In addition to government support, incentives, loans, and subsidies should be used to encourage the private sector to build more homes. It is also necessary to provide financial resources to the Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria, which is tasked with overseeing and managing the activities of Nigeria's mortgage institutions.

Building sites should also be accessible and easily available for prospective home owners. Building plans approval and the issue of a certificate of occupancy must be expedited and simplified in the same way. Additionally, promoting the mass manufacturing of construction materials is essential. This will allow the resources to be more accessible to those who cannot buy them. Individuals should be encouraged to build their own homes utilizing low-cost financing schemes as a viable alternative to mass housing. REDAN, the Nigerian Real Estate Development Association, and other housing-related organizations should be given government support to grow and prosper.

Public policy makers must also comprehend how vital policy research is to the process of building new homes. An investigation of housing policy should concentrate on the policy's goals and objectives and how they are achieved through its implementation and review. Financing strategies and programs, slum upgrading and institutional support for the building and delivery of homes are among the other recommendations. These are the tenets of environmentally friendly housing.

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